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D3.2 Catalogue of RSQKit Tools for Assessing and Improving Software Quality and FAIRness

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

For this demonstrator, we have created the initial catalogue of tools and services used to assess and improve research software quality, associated metadata and FAIRness. We have set up the technical infrastructure and processes that enable our community to suggest new tools to be included in the catalogue, and we have created initial curation guidelines on which tools should be accepted. We have created an interactive TechRadar dashboard, that allows users to easily explore this catalogue and discover tools new to them. Both, the contribution and curation mechanism and the dashboard are explained in detail in this document. In addition, we have set up a synchronization mechanism between TechRadar and RSQKit that helps us keeping the metadata between both platforms consistent.

1 Introduction

The EVERSE project aims to create a framework for Research Software and code excellence, collaboratively designed and championed by the research communities across five EOSC Science Clusters and national Research Software Expertise Centres, in pursuit of building a European network of Research Software Quality and setting the foundations of a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence.

As part of the EVERSE project, Work Package 3 (WP3) aims to connect existing individual tools and services with developers and EOSC Science Clusters in three steps:

1. Collecting existing tools and services for software (including all forms of executable code) quality,
2. Linking them in common pipelines or frameworks, and
3. Integrating them with platforms used in the EOSC Science Clusters.

In this demonstrator D3.2, we describe the initial catalogue of tools and services used to assess and improve research software quality, associated metadata and FAIRness.

The aim of this catalogue is two-fold. Firstly, thru TechRadar [1], it provides a structured, searchable, and interactive way for users to explore and discover new tools based on function, compatibility, use case and community adoption. This enables users to quickly find the tools they need, based on an (opinionated) recommendation from EVERSE.

Secondly, this catalogue serves as the master source of information on research software quality tools for RSQKit [2]. Tools present in this catalogue will be integrated into RSQKit by linking them to good practices, which contain extensive and in-depth guidelines on developing, collaborating on and improving the quality of research software. New good practices descriptions will be added if tools do not fit into existing descriptions yet.

In the following sections, we will describe the curation process that led to the current selection of tools, provide a brief overview of this current selection (as shown in the TechRadar), and describe in more detail how these tools will be adopted into RSQKit and linked to the best practices as proposed by WP2.

This deliverable is a follow-up to D3.1 [3], in which an initial list of tools and services was created, and MS8 [4], where these tools and services were evaluated in against the initial good practices, as described in MS4 [5].

2 TechRadar

In D3.1 [3], an initial list of tools and services was created that can be used to assess and improve software quality and FAIRness. For MS8 [4], a workshop was organized to evaluate this list of tools and services against the initial list of good practices, as described in MS4 [5].

The outcome of this workshop clearly identified that the users would like guidance and recommendations on such tools. For many users, the time investment required to learn a new tool can be significant, especially as there are many alternatives to choose from. Therefore, EVERSE should provide an (opinionated) recommendation on which tools to use, and present this selection in a structured, searchable, and interactive way that allows users to:

- Find tools based on function, compatibility, use case and community adoption.
- Explore and discover new tools.
- Interact dynamically with the catalogue through advanced filters, rankings, and AI-assisted recommendations.

These requirements led to the development of the TechRadar [1]. The goal of TechRadar is to create an online catalogue of tools and services designed to help measuring and improving research software quality and provide an interactive dashboard that categorizes these tools according to the quality indicators and quality dimensions recorded in their metadata.

In the following sections, we will describe the content curation process used to collect the information about tools and show how this information is presented.

2.1 Content Curation Process

The content of the TechRadar is based on input from the community (participants of the MS8 workshop), followed by a curation step by a team of experts. We use the TechRadar repository [6] to collect feedback and contributions. In the following sections we will summarize the contributing guidelines and curation process, which can also be found in the GitHub repository [7].

Although contributions can also be general (reporting issues, suggesting improvements, or providing feedback) or technical (such as bug fixes or dashboard enhancement), we will focus on the content contributions to the TechRadar catalogue.

2.1.1 Scope of the tools accepted into TechRadar

The goal of the catalogue is to include tools and services that address the unique requirements of research software, including but not limited to:

- Analysis of source code to identify potential issues, performance improvements, vulnerabilities, and adherence to coding standards specific to research contexts.
- Evaluation of software against research-specific quality attributes such as reproducibility and FAIRness [11].
- Support for general software standards and good practices relevant to specific research disciplines.
- Metrics and measurements tailored to assess both technical aspects and research-oriented factors.
- Capabilities to analyse and improve research software quality throughout the research software lifecycle, from development to long-term sustainability.

These tools aim to enhance the overall quality, reproducibility, reliability, maintainability and reusability of research software, ultimately contributing to the impact of scientific research.

2.1.2 New tool acceptance criteria

New tools must meet a specific set of criteria listed below to be included in the TechRadar. The criteria are designed to ensure that the tools and services are relevant, useful, and actively maintained for improving research software quality. To be accepted, the tool or the service:

- has been designed with the intent of measuring or improving software quality, and it does measure or improve software quality.
- is frequently used on research software.
- is being actively maintained.
- helps developers to follow relevant research software community standards and good practices.

2.1.3 Workflow to propose a new tool

To propose a new tool or service, or modify an existing one, contributors can follow the contribution guidelines described in [8]. These guidelines follow the customary “fork, pull request, review” approach for GitHub repositories.

After a pull request is ready, it will be reviewed by a member of the TechRadar curation team (@EVERSE-ResearchSoftware/techradar-curators) who may provide feedback or request changes before merging it into the main branch. The curation team will ensure the necessary documentation, in markdown format, can be generated for the newly added tools and ensuring that each file includes the appropriate quality dimension segments and filtering tags.

Once a pull request is approved, it will be merged by the curation team into the main branch. The changes will be reflected in the TechRadar dashboard at the next release.

2.1.4 Curation of proposed tools

The curation is done by a team of research software engineers and experts, currently formed of EVERSE members. We welcome new members based on their curriculum and expertise in research software development. Members of the curation team self-assign curation tasks whenever a new pull request is submitted. Weekly meetings provide the opportunity for the curators to discuss any issues they encountered, and to ensure no pull request remain unassigned.

The curators check if:

- The tool or service is worth adding into the TechRadar and that the acceptance criteria described above are met.
- The metadata are correct and that they describe the tool or service accurately.
- The tool is assigned to the correct software tier(s), as described in [12].

Once accepted, the new entry will appear in the next release of TechRadar dashboard. We plan to make a new release of the dashboard every 6 months by taking a snapshot of the catalogue. Each version of the TechRadar will be released on GitHub and archived on Zenodo.

2.2 Interactive Dashboard

The data collected in the TechRadar repository is used to generate an interactive dashboard that categorizes the collection of tools according to the quality dimensions [8] and quality indicators [9] they produce for the software under assessment. As a tool may produce multiple

indicators, it may also be presents in multiple categories in TechRadar. A screenshot is shown in Figure 1.

In the initial prototype of the TechRadar, the tools are classified into eleven categories, each corresponding to a quality dimension:

- **Compatibility:** degree to which a product, system or component can exchange information with other products, systems or components, and/or perform its required functions while sharing the same common environment and resources.
- **FAIRness:** degree to which research software adheres to the FAIR principles.
- **Flexibility:** degree to which a product can be adapted to changes in its requirements, contexts of use or system environment.
- **Functional Suitability:** degree to which a product or system provides functions that meet stated and implied needs when used under specified conditions.
- **Interaction Capability:** degree to which a product or system supports users in performing their tasks and achieving specified goals.
- **Maintainability:** degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a product or system can be modified to improve it, correct it or adapt it to changes in environment, and in requirements.
- **Performance Efficiency:** degree to which a product performs its functions within specified time and throughput parameters and is efficient in the use of resources (such as CPU, memory, storage, network devices, energy, materials, ...) under specified conditions.
- **Reliability:** Degree to which a system, product or component performs specified functions under specified conditions for a specified period of time.
- **Safety:** degree to which a product under defined conditions to avoid a state in which human life, health, property, or the environment is endangered.
- **Security:** Degree to which a product or system defends against attack patterns by malicious actors and protects information and data so that persons or other products or systems have the degree of data access appropriate to their types and levels of authorization.
- **Sustainability:** The capacity of the software to endure. In other words, sustainability means that the software will continue to be available in the future, on new platforms, meeting new needs.

Figure 1 TechRadar prototype on the EVERSE website

Figure 2 The list of tools in TechRadar Sustainability Segment

Selecting a segment on the interactive dashboard will filter all tools categorized in this segment. This allows users to quickly get an overview of related tools and alternatives. An example is shown in Figure 2, which shows the Sustainability segment.

In addition to the eleven software dimensions, the tools are also labelled according to their applicability to the three software tiers: Analysis Code, Prototype Tools, and Research Software Infrastructure [12]. This additional information is used to indicate the lowest software tier to which the tool is applicable. For example, all tools that can be used for Analysis Codes (such as a license picker) also apply to Prototype Tools or Research Software Infrastructure.

Figure 3 TechRadar Python Tag

Finally, to allow further filtering, tools are individually tagged with keywords. This allows for easy selection of tools that provide similar functionality. Figure 3 shows an example, where the “python” keyword is selected. This results in a collection of tools being shown which can be used to improve the quality of python applications. For each tool, the relevant quality dimension and applicable software tier are shown.

3 Adoption of TechRadar tools into RSQKit

The current collection of tools on the TechRadar has been compiled through the groundwork done in D3.1, MS4 and MS8. While the TechRadar provides a convenient interactive dashboard to quickly explore the available tools, the overall goal is to integrate these tools into the best practices described on RSQKit.

An example is the *CodeMeta Generator*, which is listed on the TechRadar as part of the Sustainability Dimension [13]. On the RSQKit, this tool is referenced as part of the *Software metadata* best practice [14].

It is important to note that the content and context of RSQKit is wider than that of the TechRadar. Where TechRadar is our main source for research software quality tools, RSQKit will also contain additional tools that are connected to research software quality best practices, but which are not a research software quality tool by itself. For example, common programming languages, like Python, R, etc. will be listed within the RSQKit but not be represented in the TechRadar.

To ensure all tools on TechRadar are also listed on RSQKit, a synchronization mechanism has been implemented [10] that automatically retrieves tool metadata from both TechRadar and RSQKit and highlights any differences. In this process, TechRadar serves as the master source of metadata on research software quality tools, and any corrections or additions will be made there. When RSQKit has more complete descriptions of tools they will be pushed to the TechRadar. Any tools present in TechRadar but missing from RSQKit will be integrated into RSQKit by linking them to existing best practices. New best practices descriptions will be added if tools do not fit into existing descriptions yet.

4 Conclusions and next steps

For this demonstrator, we have created the initial catalogue of tools and services used to assess and improve software quality, associated metadata and FAIRness. We have set up the technical infrastructure and processes that enable our community to suggest new tools to be included in the catalogue and created initial curation guidelines on which tools should be accepted. Using the interactive TechRadar dashboard, users can easily explore this catalogue and discover new tools.

In the coming period, the initial catalogue of tools will be further refined, their metadata and descriptions improved where needed, and additional tools added that are contributed by our community. While an initial technical connection between the tools on TechRadar and the Best Practices on RSQKit has been created, further work is needed to ensure that the content of both resources is kept sufficiently in-sync. In addition, all tools in TechRadar should be present in RSQKit and linked to the relevant best practices. Currently, this is not yet the case.

Finally, the TechRadar currently does not take quality indicators into account. Such indicators can be used to assess to what extent research software adheres to certain requirements or best practices. Annotating tools in TechRadar with the related indicators would make it easier for users find the specific tools they need to achieve a measurable software quality improvement and would also allow further automation of the integration between TechRadar and RSQKit.

5 References

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